

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF NUEVA ECILJA

EDUARDO L. JOSON MEMORIAL COLLEGE

**A Structural Model of the Factors Affecting Students'
Mathematics Performance**

An Undergraduate Thesis Presented to the Faculty of Eduardo
L. Joson Memorial College

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Mathematics

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April 2023

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ABSTRACT

The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and 2019 Trend in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) revealed that Filipino students performed poorly in mathematics compared to their counterparts in other countries. Students' mathematics performance and the factors affecting it have been studied previously but a limited number of studies investigated structural models. This study used predictive-correlational design and employed Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach to investigate the factors affecting students' mathematics performance and to propose a structural model for these factors. A survey was carried out among 309 grade 10 students of three public high schools in Nueva Ecija, Philippines. Using WarpPLS 7.0, the results of data analysis revealed that teachers' performance and use of instructional materials, and students' interest in mathematics affect mathematics performance. It is also revealed that students' interest in mathematics and teachers' use of instructional materials mediate the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance. This study proposes a structural model with meaningful predictive accuracy for the factors affecting students'

mathematics performance which can be used as basis in developing programs that will help improve students' mathematics performance.

CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the most important subjects in any all-levels education. It is seen as useful in many different ways and has been on many major education commissions and committees' reports. As part of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, all people must have access to high-quality education at all levels to empower them and create new work possibilities. Mathematics is an important tool in meeting these goals as it facilitates understanding and knowledge. The math performance of young people in their adolescent years is shaped by a multiplicity of factors both within schools and outside of them. According to the study of Eric A. Hanushek, et al, 2010, the result did not identify any single cause of the relatively small percentage of students in the U.S. who are performing at a high level of accomplishment.

Proficiency in mathematics is seen as an essential precursor to success in modern society. The Philippines, rank second to last in mathematics in the 2018 test by the Program of International Student Assessment (PISA) of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

(OECD). It also showed that Filipino students ranked the lowest among 79 countries in Mathematics. According to OECD 2018 PISA Country, fifteen-year-old students in the Philippines scored lower in Mathematics than those in most of the countries and economies that participated in PISA 2018. No country scored lower than the Philippines.

The Philippines implemented the K to 12 Program in 2013 to improve the holistic development and global competitiveness of Filipino students. The country's achievement in large-scale international tests such as the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). One indicator of the reform's efficacy is the link between the K-12 mathematics curriculum and TIMSS.

Mathematics Performance can be attributed to several factors. This study aims to examine the effects of students' interest, teachers' performance, study habits, and instructional materials on Mathematics Performance. Kihwele, J. and Mkomwa, J., (2022), Wong, (2019), Landicho (2021), Anyagh, et.al (2020), Essien, et.al (2015), Tambunan, et.al (2021) and Adam, M. et. Al (2013) found out that students' interest significantly correlates with Mathematics Performance. In contrast, a study conducted in Malaysia by Shu Ling Wong & Su Luan Wong (2019) showed a different result.

The study revealed that interest was not significantly correlated to mathematics performance among the students.

Based on the study of Sakirudeen and Sanni (2017) and Capuno et.al, 2019, There is a significant relationship between study habits and academic performance. However, the study conducted by Sayyadi (2019) found that there is no significant relationship between study habits and academic performance in mathematics.

Edoho et al., (2020), Muema (2021), Adalikwu and Iorkpilgh, (2013); Tety, (2016); Kelechi, (2016); and Onu, et.al (2020); found that teaching with instructional materials has a significant effect on students' academic performance in mathematics. Studies also showed that there is a relationship between instructional materials and academic performance. Lanchino, (2021) and Tambunan, et. al (2021) found that teacher performance is very significant in influencing student interest and motivation to be excellent in mathematics.

The researchers discovered that there is no Structural Model in the study after reviewing the prior work. As a result, the researchers will develop a structural model and assess the direct and indirect effects of the factors mentioned, as well as the sequential mediators of the study.

Theoretical Framework

The study anchored on the theory of Interest Driven Creator: Interest and Interest Loop or the IDC Theory. IDC theory is developed as a group endeavor by Asian researchers to articulate a holistic learning design theory for future education in Asia (Chan, TW., Looi, CK., Chang, B. et al., 2019). The theory hypothesized that students, driven by interest, can be engaged in the creation of knowledge (generating ideas and artifacts). By repeating this creation process in these daily learning routines, they will excel in learning performance, develop twenty-first-century competencies, and form creation habits. It is said that when learning becomes interesting for students, they will focus their attention on learning, spend time and energy, make effort without feeling that they are making effort, enjoy learning, and, consequently, excel in learning performance. Through this, connection drawn out by the theory, researchers had the idea to include the variables interest and habit that said to be factor to excel learning performance.

Conceptual Framework

According to studies, interest and academic performance has a significant relationship (Essien et. al, 2015; Tembe et. al, 2020; Tambunan et. al, 2021). Furthermore, study habit and academic performance has a significant relationship (Odiri, 2015; Sakirudeen & Dr. Bimbo, 2017; Sayyad, 2019; Capuno et. al, 2019). However, Shu Ling Wong and Su Luan Wong's (2019) study, which is anchored by IDC Theory, yields different results. According to the findings of the study, there is no significant relationship between interest and academic performance. This discovery prompted the researchers to investigate other factors that are related to academic performance.

One of external factor that influences student interest to learn is teacher factor. The teacher has important role to build student learning interest. The teacher's role is to increase student learning interest in mathematics (as cited by (Tambunan, et. al, 2021). Hardi Tambunan, Bornok Sinaga, & Wahyu Widada (2021), found out that teacher's performance in building interest significantly influences student interest to excel at mathematics. Study also suggest that Teaching skills of teacher would have positive impact on student's performance in mathematics (Landicho, 2021). In addition, Landicho (2021) identifies instructional material

as one of the teacher related factors that affects students' mathematics performance. Instructional materials play a very important role in the teaching and learning process. It enhances the memory level of the students. At this time that education has spread wide and entirely, oral teaching cannot be the key to successful pedagogy; therefore, the teacher has to use instructional materials to make teaching and learning process interesting (as cited by Offiong, 2015). John Lawrence Tety (2016), found out there is a very strong positive significant relationship between instructional resources and academic performance. In addition, he also found out that teacher with the use of instructional materials helps students in learning process. Studies also suggest that there is a significant relationship between instructional material and academic performance (Stephen A. Adalikwu & Isaac T. Iorkpilgh ,2013; Adebule & Ayoola, 2015; Edoho et. al, 2020; Judith Kavutha Muema, 2021).

The conceptual framework of the study examines the relationships among instructional materials, student interest, study habits, teachers' performance, and academic performance. The study operationalizes these constructs to provide measurable indicators for empirical investigation. The operational variable for instructional materials, as proposed by Lukman (2022), can be the presence or absence of

supplementary materials such as textbooks, visual aids, multimedia resources, and interactive tools used by teachers to facilitate instruction. Student interest, as defined by Teachmint (2021) and Kahu et al., (2017), can be assessed through self-reported Likert-scale questions measuring students' level of interest, engagement, and enthusiasm towards a specific subject or topic. Study habits, as identified by Aghaei, Jafari, and Khatony (2019), can be operationalized through a study habits questionnaire or checklist, examining behaviors such as time management, note-taking, active reading, self-testing, and organization. Teachers' performance, as assessed by Gul (2019), can be evaluated through classroom observations, self-assessment, or student evaluations, encompassing factors such as teaching effectiveness, pedagogical strategies, instructional delivery, and classroom management skills. Muema (2021) defined academic performance as the attainment of a student's level in his/her marks. Academic performance, as measured in the Philippines, utilizes the Department of Education (DepEd) grading scale outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015. This widely used tool provides a standardized means of measuring students' academic performance. By considering these operational variables, the study aims to explore the interrelationships among instructional materials, student

interest, study habits, teachers' performance, and academic performance (Landicho, 2021; Tambunan et al., 2021; Wong & Wong, 2019; Tety, 2016; Muema, 2021).

Paradigm

The paradigm for this study was supported with the theory and studies which identifies the factors affecting students' mathematics performance. Students' interest and study habits was drawn out using the concept of IDC Theory, followed by related studies. Teacher related factors such as teachers' performance and instructional materials are linked to the variable under the IDC Theory and have been supported by studies indicating that these variables are relevant to present study. Hence, these variables presumed to be directly related to students' mathematics performance. Figure 1 presents the paradigm which serves as the proposed structural model for this research.

Figure 1. A Structural Model on Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to examine the effects of teachers' Performance and use of instructional materials and students' interest in mathematics and study habits on mathematics performance. It also aims to propose a structural model on the factors affecting students' mathematics performance. Specially, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How may the students be described in terms of:
 - a. Mathematics performance?
 - b. Interest in Mathematics?
 - c. Study habits?
2. As perceived by the students, how may the teachers be described in terms of:
 - a. Performance?
 - b. Use of instructional materials?
3. Do the following variables affect students' mathematics performance:
 - a. Teachers' performance?
 - b. Teachers' use of instructional materials?
 - c. Students' interest in mathematics?
 - d. Study habits?
4. Does students' interest mediate the effect of the following variables on students' mathematics performance:

- a. Teachers' performance?
 - b. Teachers' use of instructional materials?
5. Does study habit mediate the effect of students' interest on mathematics performance?
6. Does teachers' use of instructional materials mediate the effect of teachers' performance on mathematics performance?
7. Do the following variables sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance?
- a. Teachers' use of instructional materials and students' interest
 - b. Students' interest and study habits?
 - c. Teachers' use of instructional materials, students' interest and study habits?
8. Do students' interest in mathematics and study habits sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' use of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study.

H1a. Teachers' performance affects students' mathematics performance?

H1b. Teachers' use of instructional materials affects students' mathematics performance?

H1c. Students' interest in mathematics affects students' mathematics performance?

H1d. Study habits affect students' mathematics performance?

H2a. Students' interest in mathematics mediates the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.

H2b. Students' interest in mathematics mediates the effect of teachers' use of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance.

H3. Study habits mediate the effect of students' interest on mathematics performance.

H4. Teachers' use of instructional materials mediates the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance

H5a. Teachers' use of instructional materials and students' interest in mathematics sequentially mediate the effect teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.

H5b. Students' interest in mathematics and study habits sequentially mediate the effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.

H5c. Teachers' use of instructional materials, students' interest in mathematics, and study habits sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.

H6. Students' interest in mathematics and study habits sequentially mediates the effects of teachers' use of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance.

Significance of the Study

This research will play vital role to guide the process of understanding the factors affecting Academic Performance towards Mathematics of grade 10 students from three different school in Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The said study work to believe to be significant because it will find solution to poor Academic Performance of students in Mathematics and it

will also be the guideline to the improvement of Mathematics Education here in the Philippines.

Through this research, the following are the sectors that will benefit this study:

- **SCHOOLS AND INSTITUTION.** They can modify the mathematics education effectively.
- **MATHEMATICS TEACHER.** They can improve their teaching and learning process for the application of effective leaning in mathematics.
- **RESEARCHERS.** The researchers are future mathematics teacher, that's why they will know the techniques and the factors that will affect the learning of their students that they can use in actual teaching in school.
- **FUTURE RESEARCHERS.** They will get data imparting the knowledge in the effects of the variables of this research on the academic performance towards mathematics. To improve more the mathematics learning in the Philippines.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focused on the factors affecting students' mathematics performance towards Mathematics namely students' interest in Mathematics, teachers' use of instructional material, teachers' performance and study habits at three different schools in Nueva Ecija during the School Year 2022-2023.

The Grade 10 students were the respondents of this study. There are partner schools of Eduardo L. Joson Memorial College: Bongabon National High School, Nueva Ecija High School, General Mamerto Natividad National High School. The estimated number of respondents is minimum of 100. This study limits its coverage in three selected schools of Nueva Ecija and by the means of survey questionnaire as a tool of data gathering.

Definition of Terms

In order to understand the terms used in this study, these are their meanings:

Academic Performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time. (Narad and Abdullah, 2016 as cited by Anthony Abaidoo, 2018)

Instructional Materials serves as a channel between the teacher and students in delivering instruction. They may also serve as the motivation on the teaching learning process. It is used to get attention of students and eliminate boredom. (Lukman, 2022)

Student Interest refers to the inclination of the student towards a particular subject in which he or she is easily able to connect without any hassle or hurdle. (Teachmint, 2022; Kahu et al., 2017)

Study Habit is different individual behavior in relation to studying and is a combination of study method and skill. In other words, study habits include behaviors and skills that can increase motivation and convert the study into an effective process with high returns, which ultimately increases the learning (Aghaei, A., Jafari, H., & Khatony, A. 2019)

Teachers' Performance means the behavior of a teacher which change differently with the change in surrounding environment, in such way that when a particular task is assigned to teacher, he/she successful takes action to carry out task (as cited by Gul, 2019).

Factor are variables in the study that believe to influence the result. It can also be called independent variables or explanatory variables. (STAT59, 2020)

Mediator defines as a variable that explains the relation between the predictor (independent variable) and the outcome (dependent variable), (Baron & Kenny, 1986; Holmbeck, 1997; James & Brett, 1984). In other words, a mediator is the mechanism through which predictor influence an outcome variable (as cited by Frazier et.al, 2014).

Sequential Mediation determines the relationship as better way of understanding potential links between all variables (Shin et.al 2016)

Structural Model is a diagram which consist of set of nodes and connections between nodes. It embodies the geometric describing form rather than calculating or calculating quantitative output (as cited by Govindan and Jepsen, 2016)

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents the related literature and studies after the thorough and in-depth search done by the researchers. This will also present the synthesis of the art and the definition of terms for better comprehension of the study. The chapter deals with the literature review based on study variables which includes academic performance of the students in mathematics, students' interest, instructional materials, teachers' performance, and study habits.

Students' Academic Performance

Muema (2021) defined academic performance as refers to the attainment of student level in his/her marks. Academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time (as cited by Abaidoo, A. 2018).

Based on student mathematics achievement, it describes the quality of mathematics learning. The higher student achievement score indicates the higher quality of learning. Based on the results of the Program for International Student

Assessment (PISA) assessment in 2019, it shows that mathematics score is still problematic (as cited by Tambunan et al., 2021). In terms of ranking mathematics score, it is ranked 72 out of 78 countries. According to PISA (2018) the Philippines came in second last with a score of 353, after Dominican Republic, which ranked the lowest in this category.

Students' Interest and Academic Performance

Interest is an individual's momentary experience of being captivated by an object and more lasting feelings that the object is enjoyable and worth further exploration (as cited by Kihwele, J. and Mkomwa, J., 2022). As widely believed, interest has a vital role in mathematics learning (as cited by Wong, 2019). In addition, Landicho (2021) also believed that Students interest in mathematics play a significant role in mathematics achievement.

According to study who examine the relationship of interest and students' mathematics performance by Ngutor Tembe, Paul Igber Anyagh, Benjamin Ogbole Abakpa, (2020). Result revealed that there was a significant relationship between Mathematics interest and students' achievement in Mathematics. In which they concluded that interest of students has the potential to influence the mathematics

achievement of students. Studies also showed that there is a significant relationship between interest and students' academic performance (Essien, Essien Ekpenyong, Akpan, Okon Edem, Obot, Imo Martin 2015; Tambunan, Hardi., Sinaga, Bornok., & Widada, Wahyu 2021; Adam, M., Setiawati, D., Nursalim, M. And Pratiwi, T. 2013). In contrast, study conducted in Malaysia by Shu Ling Wong & Su Luan Wong (2019) showed different result. Study revealed that interest was not significantly correlated to mathematics performance among the students.

Study Habits and Academic Performance

Sayyadi, S. (2019) define study habits as skills that a learner employs and use in order to achieve the learning aims and objectives. Additionally, study habit is the pattern of behavior adopted by students in the pursuit of their studies that serves as the vehicle of learning. It is the degree to which the students engage in regular acts of studying theta are characterized by appropriate studying routines occurring in an environment that is conducive to study (as cited by Mendezabal, 2013).

The study habit is one of the factors that could also largely influence students' performance. If this is not given

attention by the persons concerned, its effect could become more damaging to students' performance. Students need to possess good study habits to excel in life because it is the study habits of the students that aid in obtaining relevant and applicable knowledge. Thus, the absence of these skills would lead the students to poor performance in school (as cited by Capuno et.al, 2019).

Abisola Oladeni Sakirudeen, Dr. Kudirat Bimbo Sanni (2017) explored the relationship of study habits and academic performance. In this study, study habits were classified into three categories: notes taking, students use of library, and time allocation to study. The result revealed that there is a significant relationship between study habits (note taking, students' use of library, and time allocation to study) and academic performance. However, a study conducted by Sagir Ibrahim Sayyadi (2019), result revealed that there is no significant relationship between note taking and mathematics performance. Under their study, study habits were divided into 8 categories: time management, concentration, note taking, reading comprehension, test preparation and test taking, reading speed, writing skills, and test anxiety management. Result revealed that significant relationship exists only between time Management and mathematics Performance. Studies also suggest that there is a significant

relationship between study habits and academic performance (Stephen A. Adalikwu and Isaac T. Iorkpilgh, 2013; John Lawrence Tety, 2016).

Instructional Material and Academic Performance

Instructional materials are objects or devices that assist the teachers to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners (as cited by Edoho, E., Ebuara, V., Agbudu, P. et al., 2020). Additionally, Muema (2021) defined instructional material as an all form of materials comprising of animation or non-animated materials whether human or non-human in which can be used by the teacher during teaching and learning process to assist in achieving the expected learning objective.

Instructional materials are essential and significant tools needed for teaching and learning of school subjects to promote teachers' efficacy and improve students' performance. They also enable both the teachers and students to participate actively and effectively in lesson sessions (Edoho et al., 2020). Additionally, according to Muema (2021) instructional materials are very important in determining performance of students in any school. When the instructional materials are adequate, the performance will be good and vice versa.

Edoho, Abaura, Agbudu, & Inah (2020) found out that teaching with instructional materials has a significant effect on students' academic performance in mathematics. Studies also showed that there is a relationship between instructional materials and academic performance (Stephen a. Adalikwu and Isaac T. Iorkpilgh, 2013; John Lawrence Tety, 2016; Chukwuagu Kelechi, 2016; Onu, William O. Anyaegbunam, Ngozi J. and Uzoigwe, Anthony U, 2020; Judith Kavutha Muema, 2021).

Teachers' Performance and Academic Performance

Teacher's performance is use to define the observable outcomes in the classroom of this training and development or lack of it. It is the set of actions, attitudes, and behaviors in the teaching-learning environment that results in achieving educational goals for students (Merlo, 2022). A teacher's demonstrated impact on students' learning as established through student achievement test scores, observed pedagogical practices, or employer or student surveys (Cash, 2016).

According to Hussain (2016) (as cited by Landicho, 2021), teachers also affect the student performance. The

guidance from the teachers indirectly affects the performance of the students.

Tambunan, Sinaga, & Widada (2021) found out that teacher performance is very significant in influencing student interest and motivation to be excellent in mathematics. Additionally, Landicho (2021) examines the factors affecting students' performance in mathematics. Result revealed that teaching skills of teacher would have positive impact on student's performance in mathematics.

Gaps in Previous Study

The researchers identified three major gaps in the prior research and literature which include evidence gap, methodology gap and population gap.

First, the researchers found out that the previous study has Evidence Gap concerning the connection between the Students' Interest and Academic Performance. The previous research stated that there is significant relationship between students' interest and mathematics achievement according to Essien, et.al (2015) and agreed by the study of Abakpa Benjamin et.al, (2020). However, it was contradicted by the study of Shu Ling Wong & Su Luan Wong (2019) stated that there is no significant relationship between students'

interest and academic performance. Additionally, the researchers also found out another evidence gap concerning the connection between Study Habits and Academic Performance. Based on the study of Abisola Oladeni Sakirudeen, Dr. Kudirat Bimbo Sanni (2017) study habits were categorized into three parts which are note taking, use of library and time allocation to study which the result reveals that there is a significant relationship between study habits (note taking) and academic performance. In contrast, the study conducted by Sagir Ibrahim Sayyadi (2019) found out that there is no significant relationship between study habits (note taking) and academic performance in mathematics.

Second, there is a methodological gap based on a review of previous studies. According to the study that the researchers are attempting to adopt as a research design, there is a dearth of past research regarding descriptive research design on the study of Landicho, Ronnie (2021). In this study, these researchers seek to establish a new inquiry on research design with Predictive Correlational design which is more appropriate in testing the effect of a variable.

Lastly, the researchers identified a population gap on the previous study. Some of these populations have been unexplored and under-researched. The Grade 10 students appear

to be important and worthy of investigation in the context of the factors that affect mathematics performance. An investigation of this group is important because according to OECD PISA country that that fifteen-year-old students in the Philippines scored lower in Mathematics than those in most of the countries and economics. Furthermore, previous research has focused primarily to elementary, Grade 8 and grade 9.

Based on the previous studies, the factors affecting students' mathematics performance are Teachers' Performance, Students' Interest, Study Habits and Instructional Materials.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter is about the research methods that was used to conduct this study. It described the research design, locale and does the sample gathered together with the characteristics of the respondents. Also, it contains information about data gathering procedure, instrument, ethical considerations and data analysis to be followed by the researchers to conduct this study.

Research Design

The researchers used a descriptive-correlational research design that aims to provide static pictures of situations as well as establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009). This design will be used in this study to verify teachers' performance, students' interest, instructional materials and study habits as a predictor of students' mathematics performance.

The researchers employed this method to determine the significant relationship between the dependent variables (students' mathematics performance) and independent variables (students' interest, teachers' performance, teachers' use of

instructional materials, and study habits) as well as the mediating effects of the variables.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in selected high schools in the 3rd District of Nueva Ecija such as; Bongabon National High School, Nueva Ecija High School, and General Mamerto Natividad National High School.

Nueva Ecija 3rd District is located in the Central Luzon, Province of Nueva Ecija. The 3rd District is one of the four congressional districts of the Philippines in the Nueva Ecija. It also has been represented in the House of Representatives since 1987.

Figure 2: Research Locale (Bongabon National High School)

Figure 3: Research Locale (General Mamerto Natividad National High School)

Figure 4: Research Locale (Nueva Ecija High School)

Respondents of the Study

The researchers selected the junior high school students in the three selected schools in Nueva Ecija, preferably the Grade 10 students. To estimate the sufficiency of the sample

size, the researchers use the "10-times rule" method (Hair et al., 2011; Peng & Lai, 2012), wherein the sample size should be greater than 10 times the maximum number of items in any latent variable. The latent variable that has the greatest number of items is teachers' performance, with 10 items. Hence, the estimated respondents for this study must be a minimum of 100. To increase the statistical power, the researchers multiply the minimum number of respondents (100) by 3 since there are three participating schools in this study to attain a high level of accuracy; therefore, the projected number of respondents for this study will be at least 300. The researchers proportioned the 300 samples into three selected schools based on the number of populations in each school. Table 1 presents the minimum sample distribution of respondents per school.

Table 1. Distribution of Sample Size

SCHOOL	POPULATION	PERCENTAGE	SAMPLE SIZE
Nueva Ecija High School	1000	41.05%	123
General Mamerto Natividad National High School	357	14.7%	44
Bongabon National High School	1078	44.25%	133
TOTAL	2435	100%	300

However, during the actual study, a total of 309 students participated, which exceeded the initial target sample size of 300. The inverse square root and gamma-exponential methods were used to estimate sample size sufficiency (Kock & Hadaya, 2018). Using WarpPLS version 0.7, with a minimum absolute significant path coefficient of 0.17, significance level of 0.05, and power level of 0.92, the inverse square root method suggested 322 samples, while the gamma-exponential method suggested 306 samples (see Figure 5). The sample size in this study is 309, which is between 306 and 322, which indicates that it achieved sample size sufficiency.

Figure 5. Results of Inverse Square Root and Gamma-Exponential Methods

Data Gathering Procedure

A letter of request for the study was written. The researchers created a questionnaire checklist, which was validated by the subject's professor before being distributed. Because of the benefits of the survey method, the researchers conduct the research in selected Nueva Ecija schools such as Bongabon National High School, Nueva Ecija High School, and Natividad National High School. The researchers explain to the respondents the significance of their participation in the study. The researchers clarify some terms to the respondents so that the respondents can answer the questionnaire with full knowledge of their responsibility as the subject of the study. The researchers asked the respondents to be completely honest. The researchers employ a stratified random sampling method. The researchers believe that this method is the most appropriate in selecting the sample for the research because the researchers' goal is to determine the effects of the factors on students' mathematics performance in Bongabon National High School, Nueva Ecija High School, and Natividad National High School. Following the completion of the questionnaire, the researcher collected and tallied the data for interpretation. The researchers draw conclusions and make recommendations for this study based on the data.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in this study is a questionnaire that consists of five parts - profile of respondents and the constructs of students' interest, study habits, teachers' performance and use of instructional materials. The profile includes the respondents' school and their second grading mathematics grade that was used to measure their academic performance. While, the six items in student interest and the seven items for instructional materials is adopted from the study of Landicho, R. (2021). For study habits, the ten items are being adapted from the study of Sakirudeen and Sanni (2017). The teacher's performance measured using the Teachers Evaluation by Student with 10 total items. All the items in these constructs were measured using 4-point scale where 1 means strongly disagree and 4 means strongly agree. The validity and reliability of these constructs was measured through the evaluation of the measurement model.

Evaluation of the Measurement Model

Table 2 presents the coefficients of Cronbach's Alpha (CA), Composite Reliability (CR), item loading and the Average Variance Extracted (AVEs) for each latent variable. As can be seen, the coefficients of CR and CA are above 0.60. Furthermore, the item loadings are all above 0.50 and the AVEs for each latent variable have values 0.417 - 0.587 which all have CR higher than 0.6. Thus, the latent variables students' interest, study habits, teachers' performance and teachers' use of instructional materials achieved the required level for internal consistency, composite reliability and convergent validity.

Table 2. Convergent Validity and Reliability Measures

Constructs/Items	Item Loading	AVE	CR	CA
STUDENTS' INTEREST				
1. I make myself prepared for the math subject.	0.771			
2. I listen attentively to the lecture of my math teacher.	0.797			
3. I actively participate in class discussion, and board work.	0.673	0.486	0.824	0.731
5. I want to get good grades in tests, quizzes, written works, and performance.	0.624			
7. I am always excited to my math class.	0.600			

STUDY HABITS

1. I used to listen attentively while taking down notes in the class.	0.704			
2. I have developed skills for effective note taking for every lesson.	0.698			
3. I always take down notes to preserve new knowledge.	0.783			
4. I use symbols to express what my teacher says in the class.	0.609			
8. I devote extra time to learn a certain subject like mathematics.	0.538	0.417	0.831	0.762
9. I schedule my time in studying and pay more attention to certain subjects like mathematics.	0.606			
10. I set up time for other social activities so that they won't interfere with my studies.	0.541			

INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS

I learn better when...

1. my teacher writes the process on the board while explaining.	0.565			
2. I have a reference book in my hand.	0.557			
3. there is a PowerPoint presentation.	0.746	0.435	0.792	0.671
4. there are visual aids.	0.701			
5. there is a mathematical figure, tools and equipment.	0.707			

TEACHERS' PERFORMANCEMy Mathematics teacher ...

1. is prepared when he/she goes to our class.	0.776			
2. has a mastery of the subject matter.	0.741			
3. plans class time and assignment to help us to problem solve and think critically. He/she provides activities that make subject matter meaningful.	0.819			
4. is clear in giving directions and on explaining the process of the topic.	0.778			
5. allows us to be active in the classroom learning environment.	0.819	0.587	0.934	0.921
6. grades us what we deserve.	0.754			
7. help us to understand more Mathematics.	0.821			
8. give us feedback on homeworks and projects so that we know where we can improve.	0.633			
9. is creative in developing activities and lesson.	0.772			
10. encourage us to speak up and be active in class.	0.731			

All item loadings are significant at 0.001 (p<.001). AVE=average variance extracted; CR=composite reliability; CA=Cronbach's alpha

Since the acceptable factor loading is greater than or equal to 0.5, item 4 and 6 in the students' interest are deleted due to low factor loading. In addition, item 5, item 6 and item 7 in study habits are also deleted because of respondents' feedback that their school don't have library and it's not always open for the students.

Table 3. Discriminant Validity Using Fornell and Larcker Criterion

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP	1.000				
SI	0.375	0.697			
IM	0.380	0.463	0.660		
SH	0.155	0.509	0.286	0.645	
TP	0.414	0.477	0.525	0.381	0.766

MP=Mathematics Performance; SI=Students' Interest; IM=Instructional Materials; SH= Study Habits; TP=Teachers' Performance. Diagonal elements are the square root of AVE of constructs, whereas the off-diagonal elements are the correlation between constructs.

Table 3 presents the discriminant validity measures for the latent variables: students' interest, instructional materials, study habits and teachers' performance. As can be seen, the square root of AVE of each latent construct is greater than any of the correlations involving the construct. Thus, the items for the latent variables: students' interest, instructional materials, study habits and teachers' performance have discriminant validity.

Ethical Considerations

This study maintained strict ethical standards. It assured that the respondents are protected, safe and respected. Also, the respondents were not forced to participate.

The researchers assured that the identities of respondents were treated with confidentiality in accordance with Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012 Section 8. The researchers will also assure to have a letter of permission to school authorities as consent prior to conduct this study. Also, the data collected together with the method, procedures will not have any manipulation in order to know the exact result of the study.

Data Analysis

A descriptive-correlational design was used in this study to verify teachers' performance, students' interest, instructional materials and study habits as a predictor of academic performance. To quantify the responses of the respondents. Likert scale was used in the responses of respondents on factors affecting student mathematics performance with a verbal interpretation as shown in table 4 (Vagias, Wade M., 2006; Edmun Nevin 2015).

Table 4. Statistical ranges and their corresponding verbal interpretation

Rating	Statistical Ranges	Verbal Descriptions			
		Students' Interest	Study Habits	Teachers' Performance	Instructional materials
4	3.26-4.00	Very interested	Extremely evident	Excellent	Extremely effective
3	2.51-3.25	Somewhat Interested	Highly evident	Very good	Highly effective
2	1.76-2.50	Not Interested	Somehow evident	Fair	Somewhat effective
1	1.00-1.75	Not at all Interested	Not evident	poor	Not effective

In terms of students' mathematic performance, Department of Education (DepEd) grading scale were used. Dep Ed Order No. 8, s. 2015. grading scale, with its corresponding descriptors, refer to table 5.

Table 5. Grading scale and its corresponding descriptors

Marks	Students' Performance
90-100	Outstanding
85-89	Very Satisfactory
80-84	Satisfactory
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations

This study used frequency and percentage in order to describe the variables for the research question one and two in the statement of the problem. For each potential value, the number of observations was described by the mean of each question and frequency count. While, the frequency in the category is divided by the total number of participants, and then multiplied by 100 to get the percentage.

The Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach was used to estimate the parameters of the structural model. The assessment of PLS-SEM results includes evaluation of the measurement model and structural model.

The evaluation of the measurement model includes the measures of the validity and reliability of the constructs. Reliability and validity of instruments are crucial criteria which researchers need to address. Reliability was defined as consistency of measurement results. Validity is the accuracy of interpretations of results. Hence, reliability and validity analyses give researchers a hint that SEM results can be interpreted correctly (Karakaya-Ozyer, 2018).

Test for reliability was examined through internal consistency and composite reliability. Internal consistency and composite reliability represent the consistency of data across tests. The reliability method evaluates the

relationship between test variables and other factors (Hajjar, 2018). Internal reliability is achieved when the Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.6 or higher. The measure of reliability and internal consistency of the measured variables representing a latent construct. In order to achieve the construct reliability, a value of $CR \geq 0.6$ is required (Ahmad, 2016; Hajjar, 2018). Composite reliability is a measure of internal consistency in scale items (as cited by Shrestha, 2021). Composite reliability values ranging from 0.6 to 0.7 are acceptable.

In terms of validity measurements, both convergent and discriminant validity were assessed. The validity of instruments is an important matter for researchers to consider. Karakaya-Ozyer (2018) defined validity as the accuracy of the outcome of a test. The validity of a research instrument or dataset measures the coverage of actual information from the gathered or analyzed dataset. It is therefore critical to prove validity (Taherdoost, 2016).

Convergent validity is the assessment of the level of agreement between multiple indicators of the same construct. Convergent validity ensures that the variables being measured are related to the latent construct being measured (Hamid, 2017). The indicator's factor loading, composite reliability

(CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) used to evaluate convergent validity. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is higher than 0.5 but we can accept 0.4. Because Fornell and Larcker said that if AVE is less than 0.5, but composite reliability is higher than 0.6, the convergent validity of the construct is still adequate (as cited by Shrestha, 2021). Each loading must have a value of 0.5 and above (Tentama, 2020).

An instrument has good discriminant validity if the items in each latent variable are not confused by the respondents with the item in each latent variable (Kock, 2015). The measure of discriminant validity is the square root of AVE coefficient. The square root of the AVE of every latent construct should be greater than any of the correlations involving the said construct (as cited by Rasoolimanesh, 2022).

The evaluation of the structural model includes assessment of path coefficients of the model, effect sizes (f^2), collinearity, coefficient of determination (R^2), and predictive relevance (Q^2) (Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016). The p-value associated with the path coefficient must be less than .05 to be significant. Evaluation of structural model also measure the effect size. The f^2 statistics can

range from small (0.02), to medium (0.15), to large (0.35) (Cohen, 1988). Kock & Lynn (2012) proposed the full collinearity test as a comprehensive procedure for the simultaneous assessment of both vertical and lateral collinearity. If all full collinearity variance inflation factors (VIFs) are equal to or lower than 3.3, the model can be considered free from common method bias. The coefficient of determination (R^2), is the variance percentage in the outcome variable that is explained by the predictor variables that are hypothesized to affect it (Kock, 2017). In addition, the predictive relevance (Q^2) coefficient indicates the predictive accuracy of the PLS path model. Q^2 values larger than zero are meaningful. Values higher than 0, 0.25, and 0.50 depict small, medium and large predictive accuracy of the PLS path model (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2018).

A mediation analysis was also conducted to investigate the mediating effect of the mediators on the model. A sequential mediation analysis was conducted to investigate the three or more segments in the model. It measured how mediator, to some extent, absorbs the effects of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable (Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016).

WarpPLS 7.0 was used to analyze the Partial Least Squares
- Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM).

CHAPTER 4
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the study's findings and evaluates them in light of the research questions and hypotheses.

Table 6a. Students' Mathematics Performance

Marks	Frequency	Percentage	Students' Performance
90 - 100	201	65.05%	Outstanding
85 - 89	63	20.39%	Very Satisfactory
80 - 84	39	12.62%	Satisfactory
75 - 79	6	1.94%	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	0	0%	Did Not Meet Expectation

Table 6a shows the distribution of the respondents in terms on Academic Performance in Mathematics. As can be seen, respondents who got a mark between 90-100 is 201 or 65.05% which is outstanding. 63 or 20.39% of the respondents got a mark between 85-89 which is very satisfactory. 39 or 12.62% of the respondents got a mark between 80-84 which is satisfactory. While, the respondents who got a mark between 75-79 is 6 or 1.94% which is fairly satisfactory. This indicates that majority of the respondents have an outstanding performance in the class. On the other hand, only few or 1.94% of the respondents have a fairly satisfactory class performance. However, it contradicts the study of Capuno, R., et.al (2019) which revealed that the majority of

respondents' academic performance in mathematics had fairly satisfactory with a frequency of 79 out of 177 (44.63%) and 2 or 1.13% of did not meet the expectations.

Table 6b. Students' Interest in Mathematics

	Mean	Interpretation
1 I make myself prepared for the math subject.	3.09	Somewhat Interested
2 I listen attentively to the lecture of my math teacher.	3.34	Very interested
3 I actively participate in class discussion and board work.	2.84	Somewhat Interested
5 I want to get good grades in tests, quizzes, written works, and performance.	3.65	Very interested
7 I am always excited to my math class.	2.57	Somewhat Interested
Weighted Mean	3.10	Somewhat Interested

Legend: Not at all Interested (1.00-1.75); Not Interested (1.76-2.50); Somewhat Interested (2.51-3.25); Very interested (3.26-4.00)

Table 6b presents the results of a survey measuring students' interest in mathematics based on their responses to several statements. As can be seen, it can be observed that the students exhibit varying degrees of interest in different aspects of mathematics. The statement with the highest mean

score is "I want to get good grades in tests, quizzes, written works, and performance" (3.65), indicating that the students are highly motivated to excel academically in mathematics. The second-highest mean score is associated with the statement "I listen attentively to the lecture of my math teacher" (3.34), suggesting that the students demonstrate a keen interest in actively engaging with the material presented during classroom lectures. On the other hand, the statements "I make myself prepared for the math subject" (3.09) and "I actively participate in class discussion and board work" (2.84) receive relatively lower mean scores. This implies that while the students still show some interest in these areas, it may not be as strong as their motivation for achieving good grades or attentively listening to the teacher. The statement "I am always excited about my math class" receives the lowest mean score of 2.57, indicating a somewhat lower level of interest. Although the students may not consistently feel excited about their math class, their interest can still be considered present to some extent. Overall, when considering all the statements together, the weighted mean score of 3.10 suggests that the students' interest in mathematics can be described as "Somewhat Interested." This indicates that while the students display a moderate level of interest, there is room for further

cultivation and enhancement to foster a stronger passion for the subject.

Previous study of Arthin, D. and Yanney, E. (2020) who also assessed the level of interest of the students in mathematics revealed that most of students did not have interest in mathematics. However, it contradicts the study of Flores, F, (2019) which revealed that students had high interest in mathematics.

Table 6c. Study Habits on Mathematics

		Mean	Interpretation
1	I used to listen attentively while taking down notes in the class.	3.25	Highly evident
2	I have developed skills for effective note taking for every lesson.	3.05	Highly evident
3	I always take down notes to preserve new knowledge.	3.15	Highly evident
4	I use symbols to express what my teacher says in the class.	2.73	Highly evident
8	I devote extra time to learn a certain subject like mathematics.	2.71	Highly evident
9	I schedule my time in studying and pay more attention to certain subjects like mathematics.	2.85	Highly evident
10	I set up time for other social activities so that they won't interfere with my studies.	2.79	Highly evident
Weighted Mean		2.96	Highly evident

Legend: Not evident (1.00-1.75); Somehow evident (1.76-2.50); Highly evident (2.51-3.25); Extremely evident (3.26-4.00)

Table 6c presents the results of a study that investigated students' study habits in the context of mathematics. The table includes several statements related to study habits. The findings reveal that students demonstrate highly evident study habits when it comes to mathematics. The statement with the highest mean score of 3.25, "I used to

listen attentively while taking down notes in the class," indicates that students actively engage in attentive listening and note-taking during math lessons. This study habit reflects their understanding of the importance of capturing key information presented in the classroom. Other study habits, such as developing skills for effective note-taking (mean: 3.05) and always taking down notes to preserve new knowledge (mean: 3.15), also receive high mean scores, further highlighting the students' commitment to recording and retaining essential information. Although slightly lower, the study habits of using symbols to express what the teacher says in class (mean: 2.73), devoting extra time to learn specific subjects like mathematics (mean: 2.71), scheduling study time and paying more attention to certain subjects (mean: 2.85), and setting aside time for other social activities without interfering with studies (mean: 2.79) are still highly evident among the students. Overall, the weighted mean score of 2.96 confirms the highly evident nature of the students' study habits in mathematics. This supports the findings of Flores, F. (2019) that students had a good study habits. However, it contradicts to the study of Capuno, R., Necesario, R., Etcuban, J., Espina, R., Padillo, G., and Manguilimotan, R. (2019) which revealed that respondents had satisfactory study habits that suggested to improve it.

Table 6d. Teachers' Performance

	My Mathematics teacher ...	Mean	Interpretation
1	is prepared when he/she goes to our class.	3.57	Excellent
2	has a mastery of the subject matter	3.52	Excellent
3	plans class time and assignment to help us to problem solve and think critically. He/She provides activities that make subject matter meaningful.	3.39	Excellent
4	is clear in giving directions and on explaining the process of the topic.	3.45	Excellent
5	allows us to be active in the classroom learning environment.	3.43	Excellent
6	grades us what we deserve.	3.47	Excellent
7	help us to understand more Mathematics.	3.51	Excellent
8	give us feedback on home works and projects so that we know where we can improve.	3.24	Very good
9	is creative in developing activities and lesson.	3.40	Excellent
10	encourage us to speak up and be active in class.	3.40	Excellent
	Weighted Mean	3.44	Excellent

Legend: Poor (1.00-1.75); Fair (1.76-2.50); Very good (2.51-3.25); Excellent (3.26-4.00)

Table 6d presents the results of a survey that aimed to assess students' perceptions of their mathematics teacher's performance. The table includes ten statements related to various aspects of the teacher's performance, along with their mean scores and corresponding interpretations. The findings indicate that students hold an overwhelmingly positive view of their mathematics teacher's performance. The mean scores for all ten statements fall within the "Excellent" range, indicating a high level of satisfaction and appreciation among the students. According to the survey results, students perceive their mathematics teacher to be well-prepared for class (mean: 3.57) and to possess a strong mastery of the subject matter (mean: 3.52). This demonstrates the teacher's competence and ability to effectively deliver the lessons, instilling confidence and trust in their students. The students also recognize the teacher's efforts in planning class time and assignments to foster problem-solving skills and critical thinking (mean: 3.39). They appreciate the activities provided by the teacher, which make the subject matter more meaningful and engaging for them. Furthermore, the mathematics teacher is perceived as clear in giving directions and explaining the process of the topic (mean: 3.45), allowing students to actively participate in the classroom learning environment (mean: 3.43), and grading

fairly (mean: 3.47). These aspects reflect the teacher's ability to facilitate understanding, promote student engagement, and ensure a fair assessment of their work. Moreover, the students feel that their mathematics teacher helps them in understanding mathematics (mean: 3.51), encourages them to speak up and be active in class (mean: 3.40), and demonstrates creativity in developing activities and lessons (mean: 3.40). These positive perceptions highlight the teacher's dedication to fostering a supportive and stimulating learning environment. Although the mean score for providing feedback on homework and projects falls within the "Very good" range at 3.24, it still indicates that the teacher offers valuable guidance to students for their improvement. Overall, the weighted mean score of 3.44 emphasizes the excellent performance of the mathematics teacher as perceived by the students. These results showcase the teacher's effectiveness in lesson preparation, subject mastery, instructional planning, clarity of explanations, promotion of student engagement, and provision of constructive feedback. However, previous study by Batuigas, F., et.al. (2022) revealed that out of 50 teachers, 55.56% are very satisfactory. It implies that teachers can teach well.

Table 6e. Teachers' Use of Instructional Materials

INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS	Mean	Interpretation
<hr/>		
I learn better when...		
1 my teacher writes the process on the board while explaining.	3.64	Extremely effective
2 I have a reference book in my hand.	2.72	Highly effective
3 there is a PowerPoint presentation.	3.15	Highly effective
4 there are visual aids.	3.05	Highly effective
5 there is a mathematical figure, tools and equipment.	3.19	Highly effective
Weighted Mean	3.14	Highly effective

Legend: Not effective (1.00-1.75); Somewhat effective (1.76-2.50); Highly effective (2.51-3.25); Extremely effective (3.26-4.00)

Table 6e presents the effectiveness of different instructional materials used by teachers in teaching mathematics. The table shows that different instructional materials have varying degrees of effectiveness in helping students learn mathematics. "My teacher writes the process on the board while explaining" receives the highest mean score of 3.64, indicating that this instructional material is "Extremely effective" in helping students learn mathematics. This result suggests that students benefit from having the teacher break down complex concepts and processes and visually represent them on the board while explaining. "I

have a reference book in my hand" receives a mean score of 2.72, indicating that this instructional material is "Highly effective" in helping students learn mathematics. This result suggests that students may benefit from having a reference book to supplement their learning, but it may not be as effective as other instructional materials in helping them understand new concepts. "There is a PowerPoint presentation" receives a mean score of 3.15, indicating that this instructional material is "Highly effective" in helping students learn mathematics. This result suggests that visual aids like PowerPoint presentations can help students understand new concepts more easily. "There are visual aids" receives a mean score of 3.05, indicating that this instructional material is "Highly effective" in helping students learn mathematics. This result suggests that visual aids such as diagrams, graphs, and charts can be effective in helping students understand mathematical concepts. "There is a mathematical figure, tools, and equipment" receives a mean score of 3.19, indicating that this instructional material is "Highly effective" in helping students learn mathematics. This result suggests that hands-on learning experiences with mathematical tools and equipment can help students understand mathematical concepts better. Overall, the weighted mean score of 3.14 indicates that the instructional materials used

by teachers are "Highly effective" in helping students learn mathematics. However, in the study of Flores, F. (2019) it revealed that teacher had a good utilization of instructional materials.

Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance

The factors affecting students' mathematics performance were assessed through the evaluation of measurement model which involves assessment of path coefficients of the structural model, effect sizes, coefficient of determination (R^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2). Figure 6 presents the PLS path model on the factors affecting students' mathematics performance. As can be seen, the beta coefficient between teachers' performance and students' mathematics performance ($\beta=0.28$, $p<.01$), teachers' use of instructional materials and students' mathematics performance ($\beta=0.17$, $p<.01$), students' interest in mathematics and students mathematics performance ($\beta=0.21$, $p<.01$), teachers' performance and teachers' use of instructional materials ($\beta=0.54$, $p<.01$), teachers' performance and students' interest in mathematics ($\beta=0.34$, $p<.01$), teachers' use of instructional materials and students' interest in mathematics ($\beta=0.29$, $p<.01$), students interest and study habits ($\beta=0.51$, $p<.01$) are significant and positive while the beta coefficient of study habits and students' mathematics performance is positive but not significant ($\beta=0.07$, $p= 0.11$).

Figure 6. Research Model with Parameter Estimates

Table 7a. Direct Effects

Direct Effects	β	SE	p-value	f^2
H1a. TP → MP	0.277	0.055	<0.001	0.122
H1b. IM → MP	0.165	0.055	0.002	0.065
H1c. SI → MP	0.215	0.055	<0.001	0.082
H1d. SH → MP	0.070	0.056	0.107	0.013

Legend: SI = Students' Interest; SH = Study Habits; TP = Teachers' Performance; IM = Teachers' use of Instructional Materials; MP = Mathematics Performance; f^2 is Cohen's (1988) effect size: 0.02=small, 0.15=medium, 0.35=large.

Analysis of data showed that teacher performance significantly and positively affects mathematics performance ($\beta=0.277$, $p<.001$). This indicates that teachers' performance increases mathematics performance with a small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f^2 =0.122$). This finding suggests that when teachers demonstrate high levels of performance in teaching mathematics, it has a beneficial impact on students' performance in the subject. Students are more likely to achieve better outcomes when they are taught by highly competent and effective teachers. Hence, H1b is supported. This is aligned with studies conducted by Landicho (2021) and Tambunan et al. (2021), who also found that teaching performance affects students' performance in mathematics. The

result implies students perform well in mathematics when their teachers teach them well.

Use of instructional materials significantly and positively affect mathematics performance ($\beta=0.165$, $p=.002$). This indicates that instructional materials increase mathematics performance with a small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f^2 =0.065$). Hence, H1b is supported. This finding suggests that incorporating appropriate instructional materials in mathematics instruction can have a beneficial impact on students' performance in the subject. When teachers utilize instructional materials effectively, such as visual aids, interactive tools, and manipulatives, students are more likely to understand and engage with mathematical concepts, leading to improved performance. This is in congruence with a study conducted by Edoho et al. (2020), who found that use of instructional materials has a significant effect on students' academic performance in mathematics. Several studies also suggest that there is a significant relationship between instructional materials and academic performance (Stephen & Iorkpilgh, 2013; John Lawrence Tety, 2016; Chukwuagu Kelechi, 2016; Onu, William O. Anyaegbunam, Ngozi J., and Uzoigwe, Anthony, 2020; Muema, 2021). This suggest that students perform well in mathematics when their teachers

use instructional materials such as PowerPoint Presentation, Visual aids and reference book.

Students' interest significantly and positively affects mathematics performance ($\beta=0.215$, $p<.001$). This indicates that students' interest increases mathematics performance with small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f^2=0.082$). Hence, H1c is supported. This finding suggests that when students have a genuine interest in mathematics, it positively influences their performance in the subject. Students who are intrinsically motivated and engaged in learning mathematics are more likely to actively participate, invest effort, and seek a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. This is in line with previous studies that identified a significant relationship between students' interest and academic performance (Essien, Essien Ekpenyong, Akpan, Okon Edem, Obot, Imo Martin 2015; Tambunan, Hardi, Sinaga, Bornok, & Widada, Wahyu 2021; Adam, M., Setiawati, D., Nursalim, M., and Pratiwi, T. 2013). In contrast, a study conducted by Shu Ling Wong and Su Luan Wong (2019) showed different results. A study revealed that interest was not significantly correlated to mathematics performance. This finding suggests that students who are more interested in mathematics tend to perform better in the subject.

Study habits do not significantly affect mathematics performance ($\beta=0.070$, $p=.107$). Hence, H1d is not supported. This finding suggests that while study habits are important for overall academic success, they may not be a significant predictor of performance specifically in mathematics. This is in congruence with the study conducted by Sagir Ibrahim Sayyadi (2019), whose results revealed that there is no significant relationship between study habits and mathematics performance. This, however, contradicts a previous study that found a significant relationship between study habits and academic performance (Stephen A. Adaliku & Isaac T. Iorkpilgh, 2013; John Lawrence Tety, 2016; Sakirudeen & Dr. Sanni, 2017).

Table 7b. Indirect Effects

Indirect Effects	β	SE	p-value	f^2
H2a. TP → SI → MP	0.073	0.040	0.034	0.032
H2b. IM → SI → MP	0.061	0.040	0.062	0.024
H3. SI → SH → MP	0.036	0.040	0.185	0.014
H4. TP → IM → MP	0.088	0.040	0.013	0.039
H5a. TP → IM → SI → MP	0.054	0.033	0.050	0.024
H5b. TP → SI → SH → MP	0.012	0.033	0.356	0.005
H5c. TP → IM → SI → SH → MP	0.009	0.028	0.376	0.004
H6. IM → SI → SH → MP	0.010	0.033	0.377	0.004

Legend: SI = Students' Interest; SH = Study Habits; TP = Teachers' Performance; IM = Teachers' use of Instructional Materials; MP = Mathematics Performance; f^2 is Cohen's (1988) effect size: 0.02=small, 0.15=medium, 0.35=large.

Analysis of data showed that the indirect effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance are statistically significant ($\beta=0.073$, $p=.034$). This indicates that students' interest mediates the effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance with a small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f^2 =0.032$). Hence, H2a is supported. This indicates that when teachers

demonstrate high levels of performance, including subject mastery, problem-solving skills, and classroom engagement, it positively influences students' interest in mathematics. Consequently, students' increased interest in the subject leads to improved performance in mathematics.

The indirect effects of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance are not statistically significant ($\beta=0.061$, $p=.062$). This indicates that students' interest did not mediate the effects of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance. Thus, H2b is not supported. While instructional materials can directly impact students' understanding and performance in mathematics, their influence does not necessarily rely on students' interest in the subject.

The indirect effects of students' interest in students' mathematics performance are not statistically significant ($\beta=0.036$, $p=.185$). This indicates that study habits did not mediate the effects of students' interest on students' mathematics performance. Thus, H3 is not supported. While students' interest in mathematics can positively influence their study habits, the study habits themselves did not play a mediating role in enhancing mathematics performance.

The indirect effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance are statistically significant ($\beta=0.088$, $p=.013$). This indicates that instructional materials mediate the effects of teachers' performance with a small to medium effect size (Cohen's $f^2=0.039$). Thus, H4 is supported. The use of instructional materials served as a pathway through which teachers' performance influenced students' mathematics performance. These findings suggest that effective utilization of instructional materials by teachers can enhance the effect of their performance on students' mathematics outcomes.

The indirect effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance is not statistically significant ($\beta=0.012$, $p=.356$). This indicates that students' interest and study habits did not sequentially mediate the effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance. Hence, H5a is not supported. The result suggests that there is no statistically significant indirect effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance when considering the sequential mediation through students' interest and study habits. In simpler terms, the study did not find strong evidence to support the idea that the combined influence of students' interest and study habits mediates the

relationship between teachers' performance and students' performance in mathematics.

The indirect effects of teachers' performance to students' mathematics performance are not statistically significant ($\beta=0.054$, $p=.050$). This indicates that instructional materials and students' interest did not sequentially mediate the effects of teachers' performance to students' mathematics performance. Thus, H5b is not supported. The result suggests that the way teachers perform in the classroom may not have a significant indirect effect on students' mathematics performance through the combined influence of instructional materials and students' interest.

The indirect effects of teachers' performance to students' mathematics performance is not statistically significant ($\beta=0.009$, $p=.376$). This indicates that instructional materials, students' interest, and study habits did not sequentially mediate the effects of teachers' performance to students' mathematics performance. Thus, H5c is not supported. The result suggests that the effects of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance are not statistically significant when considering the sequential mediation through instructional materials, students' interest, and study habits. In simpler terms, the

study did not find strong evidence to support the idea that how well teachers perform in teaching mathematics has a significant indirect impact on students' performance through the combined influence of instructional materials, students' interest, and study habits.

The indirect effects of instructional materials to students' mathematics performance are not statistically significant ($\beta=0.010$, $p=.377$). This indicates that students' interest and study habits did not sequentially mediate the effects of instructional materials to students' mathematics performance. Thus, H6 is not supported. The result suggests that there is no statistically significant indirect effect of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance when considering the sequential mediation through students' interest and study habits. In simpler terms, the study did not find strong evidence to support the idea that the influence of instructional materials on students' performance in mathematics is mediated by the combined influence of students' interest and study habits.

This study also found no significant sequential mediation among the factors affecting students' mathematics performance. This suggest that these factors may have a direct or indirect impact on the students' performance in

mathematics. The factors may work independently or interact with each other to influence students' mathematics performance. Therefore, it is important to identify and address each factor separately to improve students' mathematics performance.

Table 8. Collinearity Assessment, Coefficient of Determination, and Predictive Relevance

Constructs	Full Collinearity VIF	R²	Q²
Mathematics Performance	1.317	0.282	0.258
Students' Interest	1.732	0.299	0.302
Study Habit	1.412	0.262	0.262
Teachers' Performance	1.660		
Instructional Materials	1.540	0.287	0.288

Table 8 presents the coefficients of full collinearity VIFs, coefficient of determination (R²), and predictive relevance (Q²) for the variables in this study. As can be seen, the full collinearity VIFs of Mathematics Performance, Students' Interest, Study Habit, Teachers' Performance, and Instructional Materials range from 1.317 to 1.732, all lower than 3.3. Hence, the measurement model is said to have no vertical and lateral collinearity. In addition, the R²

coefficient for Mathematics Performance is 0.282. This indicates that 28.2% of the variance in Mathematics Performance can be explained by the predictors- Students' Interest, Study Habit, Teachers' Performance, and Instructional Materials. The R^2 coefficient for Students' Interest is 0.299. This indicates that 29.9% of the variance in Students' Interest can be explained by the predictors - Teachers' Performance and Instructional Materials. The R^2 coefficient for Study Habit is 0.262. This indicates that 26.2% of the variance in Study Habit can be explained by Students' Interest. The R^2 coefficient for Instructional Materials is 0.287. This indicates that 28.7% of the variance in Instructional Materials can be explained by Teachers' Performance. Furthermore, as can be seen, the Q^2 coefficient for Mathematics Performance is 0.258, Q^2 coefficient for Students' Interest is 0.302, Q^2 coefficient for Study Habit is 0.262, and the Q^2 coefficient for Instructional Materials is 0.288. This indicates the predictive accuracy for Mathematics Performance, Students' Interest, Study Habit, and Instructional Materials is meaningful.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents a brief overview of the whole study, focusing on the research topic, research methods, findings, key contributions of the research, and recommendations for future work.

Summary of Findings

The following findings are drawn from the analyzed and interpreted data:

1. The respondents demonstrated outstanding performance in mathematics, with a majority achieving marks between 90-100. Their interest in mathematics varied, with a moderate level of engagement. They displayed strong study habits, including attentive listening and effective note-taking.
2. The students perceived their mathematics teachers to have excellent performance, being well-prepared, and possessing a strong mastery of the subject matter. The instructional materials used by teachers were highly effective, with board explanations being the most impactful.
3. Teachers' performance, use of instructional materials, and students' interest in mathematics had

a significant positive effect on students' mathematics performance. However, study habits did not show a significant relationship with mathematics performance.

4. Students' interest played a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' performance and students' mathematics performance, while instructional materials did not mediate this relationship.
5. Study habits did not mediate the effect of students' interest on mathematics performance.
6. Teachers' use of instructional materials did not mediate the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.
7. None of the examined variables sequentially mediated the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance.
8. Students' interest and study habits did not sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' use of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to determine the factors affecting students' mathematics performance. This study utilized a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design approach. Based on the findings, it can be concluded the following:

1. The respondents in this study exhibited outstanding performance in mathematics, with a majority achieving marks between 90-100. This indicates a high level of mathematical proficiency among the students. The respondents displayed varying degrees of interest in mathematics, with a moderate level of engagement. While they were motivated to excel academically, their active participation and preparation in class discussions were relatively lower. This suggests the potential for further cultivation of interest in the subject. Strong study habits were observed among the respondents, including attentive listening, effective note-taking, and dedicating extra time to learning mathematics. These study habits reflect their commitment to effective learning strategies.
2. The students perceived their mathematics teachers to have excellent performance in teaching. Teachers were well-prepared for class, possessed a strong mastery of

the subject matter, and effectively explained topics. The instructional materials used by teachers were also deemed highly effective in enhancing students' learning experience.

3. Teachers' performance, teachers' use of instructional materials, and students' interest in mathematics have a significant positive effect on students' mathematics performance. Effective teacher performance and the use of instructional materials enhance students' understanding and achievement in mathematics. Students' interest in the subject also plays a crucial role in their performance.

4. Students' interest plays a mediating role in the relationship between teachers' performance and students' mathematics performance. When teachers exhibit high performance, including subject mastery, problem-solving skills, and active classroom engagement, students' interest in mathematics is heightened, leading to improved performance in the subject. However, the analysis did not reveal a mediating effect of students' interest in the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' mathematics performance. This suggests that while instructional materials directly impact students' understanding and

performance in mathematics, they do not necessarily influence students' interest in the subject.

5. The analysis did not find evidence to suggest that study habits mediate the effect of students' interest on mathematics performance. This indicates that while students' interest in mathematics may positively influence their study habits, the study habits themselves do not play a mediating role in enhancing mathematics performance.
6. The mediating effect of teachers' use of instructional materials in the relationship between teachers' performance and students' mathematics performance. This suggests that the impact of teachers' performance on mathematics performance is not mediated by the use of instructional materials. In other words, teachers' performance directly influences students' mathematics performance, regardless of the extent to which instructional materials are utilized. Therefore, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of teachers' performance in terms of subject mastery, problem-solving skills, and classroom engagement has a direct impact on students' mathematics performance, independent of the use of instructional materials.

7. Teachers' use of instructional materials and students' interest, students' interest and study habits, and the combined influence of teachers' use of instructional materials, students' interest, and study habits, sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' performance on students' mathematics performance. This means that the impact of teachers' performance on mathematics performance is not sequentially influenced or mediated by these factors. The findings suggest that the direct relationship between teachers' performance and students' mathematics performance may be the primary driver of academic outcomes in this context.
8. Students' interest in mathematics and study habits do not sequentially mediate the effect of teachers' use of instructional materials on students' mathematics performance. This means that the relationship between teachers' use of instructional materials and students' mathematics performance is not influenced or mediated by students' interest and study habits in a sequential manner. These findings suggest that the impact of teachers' use of instructional materials on mathematics performance may have a direct effect or may be influenced by other factors not included in this study.

9. The research model was able to predict the effect of these factors to students' mathematics performance with large predictive accuracy.

Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers may consider focusing on enhancing their performance in teaching mathematics. This can involve continuous professional development to improve subject mastery, problem-solving skills, and classroom engagement. Collaborating with fellow educators, exploring innovative teaching approaches, and incorporating interactive learning activities can contribute to creating an engaging and effective mathematics learning environment. Additionally, involving students in goal-setting and self-assessment activities can empower them in their learning journey and promote a growth mindset. By making efforts to improve their teaching practices, teachers can positively impact students' mathematics performance and foster a supportive learning atmosphere.

2. It is suggested that educators consider placing emphasis on fostering students' interest in mathematics. Various strategies can be employed by teachers to engage students, such as relating mathematical concepts to real-life applications, incorporating hands-on activities, and providing opportunities for student participation and exploration. By cultivating students' interest, their motivation and performance in mathematics can be positively impacted. Additionally, the integration of educational games into the curriculum may enhance the learning experience and further develop students' interest in mathematics. Games can make learning more enjoyable, interactive, and immersive, creating a positive learning environment that stimulates students' curiosity and enthusiasm. By incorporating games that align with mathematical concepts and skills, teachers can potentially foster a sense of fun and excitement in the classroom, ultimately enhancing students' engagement and interest in the subject.

3. It is advisable to encourage students to develop effective study habits and learning strategies. Although study habits did not show a significant direct effect on mathematics performance in this study, they still hold value for overall academic success. Guidance on note-

taking techniques, time management, and self-directed learning can be provided by teachers and parents to help students optimize their study habits.

4. Schools and educational institutions may consider providing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their teaching skills and knowledge in mathematics education. This can include workshops, seminars, and collaborative learning experiences that focus on effective instructional strategies, the use of instructional materials, and the fostering of student interest.
5. Further research is recommended to explore additional factors that may affect mathematics performance. This can include investigating the effect of parental involvement, classroom environment, and student-teacher relationships on students' performance in mathematics. Understanding these factors can provide valuable insights for developing comprehensive approaches to improve mathematics education.
6. It is recommended to consider the use of a structural model as a conceptual basis in future studies. A structural model provides a framework for analyzing the relationships among variables and can offer a deeper understanding of the complex factors influencing

mathematics performance. By employing a structural model, researchers can examine the direct and indirect effects of various factors on students' mathematics performance. This can contribute to the development of more comprehensive interventions and strategies aimed at improving mathematics education.

Limitations of the Study

The study has several limitations that should be taken into account when interpreting the findings. Firstly, the sample used in the study consisted of individuals who demonstrated a high level of performance in mathematics. While this indicates a strong performance, it may not accurately represent the entire population of students, particularly those who struggle with mathematics. This limits the generalizability of the findings to students with lower levels of performance, and future studies should aim for a more diverse sample to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting mathematics performance across different performance levels.

Another limitation is the subjective assessment of teacher performance. The evaluation of teacher performance in this study was solely based on the perceptions and evaluations

of the students. While student feedback provides valuable insights, it is subjective and can be influenced by personal biases, preferences, and prior experiences. Relying solely on student assessments may not capture the full range of a teacher's abilities and effectiveness. To obtain a more comprehensive and balanced evaluation, future research should consider incorporating multiple sources of assessment, such as peer evaluations or objective measures of teaching effectiveness.

Additionally, the study lacked pilot testing, which could have identified potential issues or flaws in the research design, survey instruments, or data collection procedures. Pilot testing allows for refining research instruments, ensuring clarity of questions, and addressing any ambiguities or inconsistencies. Furthermore, it was found that one of the variables, study habits, did not statistically significantly relate to the dependent variable. This may be due to the inclusion of an irrelevant statement or outdated measure in assessing study habits. Future research should utilize updated and validated measures to assess study habits and ensure their relevance to the research context.

Lastly, the questionnaire used to measure the use of instructional materials in this study primarily focused on

visual learners, neglecting other learning styles such as auditory or kinesthetic. This limitation restricts the comprehensive assessment of the effect of instructional materials on mathematics performance, as different students may respond differently to various modes of instruction. By not accounting for the diverse learning preferences and needs of students, the study's findings may not fully capture the effectiveness of instructional materials across the entire student population. Future research should employ a more inclusive approach by incorporating assessment tools that consider a broader range of learning styles, allowing for a more holistic understanding of the relationship between instructional materials and mathematics performance.

These limitations emphasize the need for caution when interpreting the study's findings. They also present opportunities for future research to address these limitations and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting mathematics performance.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A. Letter to School Heads

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF NUEVA ECIJA
EDUARDO L. JOSON MEMORIAL COLLEGE

February 13, 2023

MS. ROSALINA M. LANORIO
School Principal
General Mamerto Natividad National High School

Dear Ma'am Lanorio:

Greetings!

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in Mathematics, we, the undersigned, are conducting a research study entitled, "**A Structural Model of Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance**". This study aims to examine the effects of students' interest, teachers' performance, study habits, and instructional materials on Mathematics Performance. It also aims to propose a structural model of the Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance.

In connection to this, may we invite **Grade 10 students** from your school as participants in our study? Data gathering will be done through survey and will be held during the students' free time. Rest assured that all information will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used for this research purposes only.

Thank you very much in anticipation of your most favorable response.

Sincerely,

Alcantara, Charlene C.

Domingo, Lealyn Q.

Meradios, John Kenneth T.

Ortega, Shelly Mae T.

Prochina, Elmer A.

Noted:

Ms. Lalaine Mae Casta
Research Adviser

Ms. Katrina M. Lajom
Chair, Teacher Education

Mrs. Danica Anie B. Lorenzo
Dean, Academic Affairs

LORENA V. SORIBAT

February 13, 2023

LORENZO P. JOAQUIN, MAEd
 School Principal IV

Dear Sir Joaquin:

Greetings!

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in Mathematics, we, the undersigned, are conducting a research study entitled, "**A Structural Model of Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance**". This study aims to examine the effects of students' interest, teachers' performance, study habits, and instructional materials on Mathematics Performance. It also aims to propose a structural model of the Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance.

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Thank you very much in anticipation of your most favorable response.

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Domingo, Lealyn Q.

Meradios, John Kenneth T.

Ortega, Shelly Mae T.

Prochina, Elmer A.

Noted:

Ms. Lalaine Mae Casta
 Research Adviser

Ms. Katrina M. Lajom
 Chair, Teacher Education

Mrs. Danica Anie B. Lorenzo
 Dean, Academic Affairs

NUEVA ECIIJA HIGH SCHOOL

RECEIVED
 1/13/23

OFFICE OF THE PRINCIPAL

February 13, 2023

ELADIO R. SANTIAGO, Ph.D
 School Principal IV
 Bongabon National High School

Dear Dr. Santiago:

Greetings!

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in Mathematics, we, the undersigned, are conducting a research study entitled, "**A Structural Model of Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance**". This study aims to examine the effects of students' interest, teachers' performance, study habits, and instructional materials on Mathematics Performance. It also aims to propose a structural model of the Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance.

In connection to this, may we invite **Grade 10 students** from your school as participants in our study? Data gathering will be done through survey and will be held during the students' free time. Rest assured that all information will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used for this research purposes only.

Thank you very much in anticipation of your most favorable response.

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Meradios, John Kenneth T.

Ortega, Shelly Mae T.

Prochina, Elmer A.

Noted:

Ms. Lalaine Mae Casta
 Research Adviser

Ms. Katrina M. Lajom
 Chair, Teacher Education

Mrs. Danica Anie B. Lorenzo
 Dean, Academic Affairs

BONGABON NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
RECEIVED
 DATE: FEB. 14, 2023
 BY:

Appendix B. Letter to the Respondents

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES
PROVINCE OF NUEVA ECIJA
EDUARDO L. JOSON MEMORIAL COLLEGE

SURVEY CONSENT FORM

We need this consent form in order to confirm that you are fully aware of the reason for your participation and that you accept its terms. Therefore, in order to confirm that you agree with the following, would you please read the information that is included before signing this form:

- All the information provided will be treated with utmost confidentiality and for academic purposes only.
- The data will be stored within a period of 1 semester only;
- Only the participating researchers and any potential academic collaborators in the study process will have access to the survey;
- The researchers will dispose the paper used in survey properly.

Appendix C. Consent Form

CONSENT

By signing below, I hereby acknowledge that I have completely read and fully understand the consent form agreement.

Participant's Signature Over Printed Name

Date

Appendix D. Data Gathering Instrument

A Structural Model of the Factors Affecting Students' Mathematics Performance

Name (Optional): _____ 2nd Quarter Grade in Math: ____

School: _____

Direction: Kindly fill up the following and put a check (✓) on the following information which implies to you. Use the rating scale in assessing students' interest, teachers' performance, instructional materials and Study Habits.

4 = Strongly Agree 3 = Agree 2 = Disagree 1 = Strongly Disagree

STUDENTS' INTEREST					
		4	3	2	1
1	I make myself prepared for the math subject.				
2	I listen attentively to the lecture of my math teacher.				
3	I actively participate in class discussion and board work.				
4	I clarify to my math teacher what I did not understand.				
5	I want to get good grades in tests, quizzes, written works, and performance.				
6	I get frustrated when the discussion is interrupted or the teacher is absent.				
7	I am always excited to my math class.				

INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS					
I learn better when...		4	3	2	1
1	my teacher writes the process on the board while explaining.				
2	I have a reference book in my hand.				
3	there is a PowerPoint presentation.				
4	there are visual aids.				
5	there is a mathematical figure, tools and equipment.				

STUDY HABITS					
		4	3	2	1
1	I used to listen attentively while taking down notes in the class.				
2	I have developed skills for effective note taking for every lesson.				
3	I always take down notes to preserve new knowledge.				
4	I use symbols to express what my teacher says in the class.				
5	I make use the library to expand the scope of my study.				

6	I study in the library every day.				
7	I used to do my assignment at the library.				
8	I devote extra time to learn a certain subject like mathematics.				
9	I schedule my time in studying and pay more attention to certain subjects like mathematics.				
10	I set up time for other social activities so that they won't interfere with my studies.				

TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE					
My Mathematics teacher ...		4	3	2	1
1	is prepared when he/she goes to our class.				
2	has a mastery of the subject matter.				
3	plans class time and assignment to help us to problem solve and think critically. He/She provides activities that make subject matter meaningful.				
4	is clear in giving directions and on explaining the process of the topic.				
5	allows us to be active in the classroom learning environment.				

6	grades us what we deserve.				
7	help us to understand more Mathematics.				
8	give us feedback on home works and projects so that we know where we can improve.				
9	is creative in developing activities and lesson.				
10	encourage us to speak up and be active in class.				

Appendix E. Inverse Square Root and Gamma-Exponential Methods

Appendix F. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Original Scales)

Indicator loading

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP	Type (as defined)	SE	P value
AP	(1.000)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Formative	0.049	<0.001
SI1	0.003	(0.743)	-0.011	-0.049	-0.029	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SI2	0.087	(0.779)	0.085	-0.077	0.015	Formative	0.050	<0.001
SI3	0.071	(0.671)	-0.080	-0.122	-0.071	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SI4	-0.054	(0.502)	-0.080	0.221	0.007	Formative	0.053	<0.001
SI5	0.135	(0.572)	0.189	-0.232	0.156	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SI6	-0.293	(0.229)	-0.004	0.124	-0.095	Formative	0.055	<0.001
SI7	-0.163	(0.616)	-0.115	0.279	-0.022	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM1	0.058	0.233	(0.565)	-0.221	0.363	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM2	-0.033	0.175	(0.557)	0.166	-0.181	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM3	0.105	-0.265	(0.746)	0.096	0.010	Formative	0.051	<0.001
IM4	-0.064	-0.022	(0.701)	-0.068	-0.110	Formative	0.051	<0.001
IM5	-0.068	-0.022	(0.707)	0.012	-0.049	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SH1	0.233	0.019	0.130	(0.643)	-0.073	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH2	0.237	0.119	-0.020	(0.568)	0.058	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH3	0.270	0.044	0.122	(0.634)	0.074	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH4	0.264	0.172	-0.122	(0.539)	0.025	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH5	-0.248	-0.147	0.038	(0.604)	-0.091	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH6	-0.224	-0.217	-0.005	(0.506)	-0.294	Formative	0.053	<0.001
SH7	-0.268	-0.223	-0.008	(0.523)	-0.261	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH8	-0.077	-0.047	-0.014	(0.558)	0.070	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH9	-0.085	0.111	-0.077	(0.617)	0.153	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH10	-0.190	0.141	-0.087	(0.520)	0.311	Formative	0.052	<0.001
TP1	0.039	-0.033	0.073	-0.013	(0.776)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP2	0.165	-0.066	-0.007	-0.077	(0.741)	Formative	0.051	<0.001
TP3	-0.012	-0.012	0.100	0.028	(0.819)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP4	-0.012	-0.144	0.180	0.080	(0.778)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP5	-0.041	0.047	0.003	-0.036	(0.819)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP6	0.117	0.010	-0.089	0.027	(0.754)	Formative	0.051	<0.001
TP7	0.063	-0.005	0.039	-0.014	(0.821)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP8	-0.088	0.048	-0.089	0.183	(0.633)	Formative	0.052	<0.001
TP9	-0.108	0.064	-0.060	-0.079	(0.772)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP10	-0.138	0.100	-0.189	-0.072	(0.731)	Formative	0.051	<0.001

Average Variance Extracted, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
Composite reliab.	1.000	0.794	0.792	0.829	0.934
Cronbach's alpha	1.000	0.699	0.671	0.771	0.921
Avg. var. extrac.	1.000	0.374	0.435	0.329	0.587

Square Root of Average Variance Extracted

Correlations among I.vs. with sq. rts. of AVEs					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP	(1.000)	0.349	0.380	-0.017	0.414
SI	0.349	(0.612)	0.446	0.428	0.467
IM	0.380	0.446	(0.660)	0.152	0.525
SH	-0.017	0.428	0.152	(0.573)	0.200
TP	0.414	0.467	0.525	0.200	(0.766)

Appendix G. Evaluation of Measurement Model (Revised Scales)

Indicator loading

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP	Type (as defined)	SE	P value
AP	(1.000)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Formative	0.049	<0.001
SI1	-0.027	(0.749)	-0.014	-0.041	-0.037	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SI2	0.066	(0.784)	0.083	-0.067	0.008	Formative	0.050	<0.001
SI3	0.042	(0.679)	-0.082	-0.112	-0.079	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SI4	-0.039	(0.485)	-0.076	0.243	0.007	Formative	0.053	<0.001
SI5	0.117	(0.586)	0.185	-0.231	0.151	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SI7	-0.181	(0.610)	-0.115	0.289	-0.027	Formative	0.052	<0.001

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP	Type (as defined)	SE	P value
AP	(1.000)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	Formative	0.049	<0.001
SI1	-0.044	(0.771)	-0.033	0.029	-0.046	Formative	0.050	<0.001
SI2	0.064	(0.797)	0.074	0.011	0.005	Formative	0.050	<0.001
SI3	0.064	(0.673)	-0.091	-0.138	-0.054	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SI5	0.143	(0.624)	0.177	-0.114	0.147	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SI7	-0.249	(0.600)	-0.137	0.221	-0.039	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM1	0.068	0.239	(0.565)	-0.139	0.358	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM2	-0.077	0.158	(0.557)	0.179	-0.196	Formative	0.052	<0.001
IM3	0.120	-0.258	(0.746)	0.038	0.014	Formative	0.051	<0.001
IM4	-0.058	0.009	(0.701)	-0.106	-0.095	Formative	0.051	<0.001
IM5	-0.063	-0.053	(0.707)	0.034	-0.052	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SH1	0.111	-0.055	0.125	(0.704)	-0.168	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SH2	0.135	-0.003	-0.019	(0.698)	-0.036	Formative	0.051	<0.001
SH3	0.156	-0.096	0.127	(0.783)	-0.030	Formative	0.050	<0.001
SH4	0.167	0.085	-0.118	(0.609)	-0.045	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH8	-0.205	-0.120	-0.002	(0.538)	0.002	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH9	-0.210	0.092	-0.084	(0.606)	0.087	Formative	0.052	<0.001
SH10	-0.295	0.134	-0.093	(0.541)	0.260	Formative	0.052	<0.001
TP1	0.033	-0.050	0.074	0.037	(0.776)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP2	0.192	-0.066	-0.005	-0.093	(0.741)	Formative	0.051	<0.001
TP3	-0.009	-0.004	0.098	0.009	(0.819)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP4	-0.031	-0.119	0.177	0.054	(0.778)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP5	-0.042	0.016	0.011	0.002	(0.819)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP6	0.107	0.023	-0.094	0.025	(0.754)	Formative	0.051	<0.001
TP7	0.063	-0.038	0.047	0.024	(0.821)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP8	-0.106	0.014	-0.082	0.176	(0.633)	Formative	0.052	<0.001
TP9	-0.094	0.075	-0.063	-0.089	(0.772)	Formative	0.050	<0.001
TP10	-0.130	0.161	-0.203	-0.127	(0.731)	Formative	0.051	<0.001

Average Variance Extracted, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach's Alpha

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
Composite reliab.	1.000	0.824	0.792	0.831	0.934
Cronbach's alpha	1.000	0.731	0.671	0.762	0.921
Avg. var. extrac.	1.000	0.486	0.435	0.417	0.587

Square Root of Average Variance Extracted

Correlations among I.vs. with sq. rts. of AVEs					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP	(1.000)	0.375	0.380	0.155	0.414
SI	0.375	(0.697)	0.463	0.509	0.477
IM	0.380	0.463	(0.660)	0.286	0.525
SH	0.155	0.509	0.286	(0.645)	0.381
TP	0.414	0.477	0.525	0.381	(0.766)

Appendix H. Evaluation of Structural model

Direct Effects

Path coefficients					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.215	0.165	0.070	0.277
SI			0.286		0.338
IM					0.536
SH		0.512			
TP					
P values					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		<0.001	0.002	0.107	<0.001
SI			<0.001		<0.001
IM					<0.001
SH		<0.001			
TP					
Standard errors for path coefficients					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.055	0.055	0.056	0.055
SI			0.054		0.054
IM					0.052
SH		0.053			
TP					
Effect sizes for path coefficients					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.082	0.065	0.013	0.122
SI			0.133		0.166
IM					0.287
SH		0.262			
TP					

Indirect Effects

* Indirect and total effects *					

Indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.036	0.061		0.161
SI					0.153
IM					
SH			0.146		0.173
TP					
Number of paths with 2 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		1	1		2
SI					1
IM					
SH			1		1
TP					
P values of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.185	0.062		0.002
SI					<0.001
IM					
SH			<0.001		<0.001

TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.040	0.040		0.055
SI					0.039
IM					
SH			0.039		0.039
TP					
Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.014	0.024		0.071
SI					0.075
IM					
SH			0.042		0.066
TP					
Indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.010		0.045
SI					
IM					

SH					0.078
TP					
Number of paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			1		2
SI					
IM					
SH					1
TP					
P values of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.377		0.165
SI					
IM					
SH					0.008
TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.033		0.046
SI					
IM					
SH					0.032
TP					

Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.004		0.020
SI					
IM					
SH					0.030
TP					
Indirect effects for paths with 4 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP					0.006
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Number of paths with 4 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP					1
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					

P values of indirect effects for paths with 4 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP					0.423
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 4 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP					0.028
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 4 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP					0.002
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					

TP > IM removed

Indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.036	0.061		0.073
SI					
IM					
SH			0.146		0.173
TP					
Number of paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		1	1		1
SI					
IM					
SH			1		1
TP					
P values of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.185	0.062		0.034
SI					
IM					
SH			<0.001		<0.001
TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.040	0.040		0.040
SI					
IM					
SH			0.039		0.039
TP					
Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.014	0.024		0.032
SI					
IM					
SH			0.042		0.066
TP					

Indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.010		0.012
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Number of paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			1		1
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
P values of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.377		0.356
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.033		0.033
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					
Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 3 segments					

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP			0.004		0.005
SI					
IM					
SH					
TP					

TP > SI removed

Indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.036	0.100		0.088
SI					0.250
IM					
SH			0.239		
TP					
Number of paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		1	1		1
SI					1
IM					
SH			1		
TP					
P values of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.185	0.006		0.013
SI					<0.001
IM					
SH			<0.001		
TP					
Standard errors of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.040	0.040		0.040
SI					0.039
IM					
SH			0.039		
TP					
Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					
	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
MP		0.014	0.039		0.039
SI					0.119
IM					
SH			0.068		
TP					

Appendix I. Collinearity Assessment, Coefficient of Determination, and Predictive Relevance

	MP	SI	IM	SH	TP
R-squared	0.282	0.299	0.287	0.262	
Full collin. VIF	1.317	1.732	1.540	1.412	1.660
Q-squared	0.258	0.302	0.288	0.262	